

STUDIES IN CARBOHYDRATES. PART VI. COMPOSITION OF THE MUCILAGE FROM SEEDS OF *MIMOSA PUDICA*

BY R. K. HULVALKAR, T. R. INGLE AND B. V. BHIDE

The mucilage from the seeds of *Mimosa pudica* is composed of D-xylose and D-glucuronic acid in the proportion of 5 : 1 molecules. Its periodate oxidation indicates a branched structure.

Mimosa pudica, Linn. (N.O. Mimoseae), commonly known as Lajalu or Lajawanti in Hindi, is found growing abundantly in hotter parts of India. The seeds have some value in Ayurvedic medicine.

The seeds contain a large amount of mucilageneous matter and swell enormously in contact with water. The mucilage is found to be firmly attached to the seeds and cannot be separated even by hard pressing. The microscopic examination of the swollen seeds reveals that the mucilage is present in a network of fibres, clinging to the seeds. The crude mucilage was extracted with water and the aqueous extract was poured into alcohol, when it was obtained as an ash-coloured powder. It is non-reducing, neutral and does not contain sulphur, nitrogen, methoxyl or acetyl group. It has an ash content of 18.6%, which is composed of Fe^{3+} , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} and SiO_2 . An ash-free mucilage was obtained more easily by extracting it from the seeds with 2% NaOH and precipitating it by alcohol containing HCl. It did not respond to tests for galactan and methylpentosan, but gave positive tests for pentosans.

Hydrolysis of the mucilage by 10% sulphuric acid afforded mainly D-xylose, which was obtained in a crystalline form and characterised by preparing its osazone and dimethylacetal of dibenzylidene-D-xylose. Traces of glucose could also be detected chromatographically. The hydrolysate furnished a uronic acid (isolated as the barium salt) which was identified as D-glucuronic acid. No other uronic acid or sugar could be detected on careful chromatographic examination.

The quantitative estimation of different sugars indicates that the mucilage is composed of D-xylose and D-glucuronic acid in the molecular proportion of 5 : 1 respectively. The oxidation of the mucilage by sodium metaperiodate afforded for one equivalent of the mucilage two molecules of formic acid and consumed five molecules of the oxidant. These results indicate that the mucilage possesses a branched structure.

EXPERIMENTAL

Isolation of the Crude Mucilage.—The seeds (500 g.) were kept in contact with water (4 litres) overnight under toluene. The thick mass, thus obtained, was disintegrated in a Waring blender. The extract was squeezed through muslin and added to alcohol (90%) when the mucilage separated as a thick mass. On trituration with absolute alcohol, it was obtained as an ash-coloured powder, yield 45 g. Its aqueous solution was non-reducing and neutral to litmus. It contained 18.6% ash and found to be composed of SiO_2 , 64% ; Fe^{3+} , 14% ; Ca^{2+} , 7.9% and Mg^{2+} , 1.4%.

Isolation and Examination of the Pure Mucilage.—The seeds (500 g.) were kept in contact with 2% NaOH solution (4 litres) overnight. The material was squeezed through a fine cloth and the extract was made acidic to Congo red with HCl. It was added to alcohol (8 litres) with stirring when the mucilage separated as a stringy mass. On trituration with absolute alcohol, it was obtained as a dry powder, yield 18.5 g. Two or three similar treatments gave the pure mucilage (yield 15 g., ash 0.1%, mainly Fe^{3+}). Its aqueous solution was non-reducing and acidic to litmus; equiv., 935; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, +24° (c, 1.5% in 1% NaOH). It did not respond to the mucic acid test for galactan and Rosenthaler's test for methylpentosan, but gave strong phloroglucinol test, orcinol test and aniline acetate test for pentoses (cf. Ingle and Bhide, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 939).

Hydrolysis of the Mucilage by 10% H_2SO_4 .—The mucilage (4 g.) was suspended in 10% H_2SO_4 (100 c.c.) at room temperature overnight, and heated at 50°. The rate of hydrolysis was followed by estimating the reducing sugars by Bertrand's method. After complete hydrolysis (5 hours), the hydrolysate was worked up in the usual manner (vide Ingle and Bhide, *loc. cit.*) and the non-acidic reducing sugars were obtained as a syrup (A), while the uronic acid was isolated as its barium salt (B).

The Syrup (A).—A chromatographic examination of the syrup indicated the presence of xylose with a trace of glucose. The presence of xylose was further confirmed by obtaining the characteristic boat-shaped crystals of cadmium bromide-cadmium xylonate (Bertrand, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1891, iii, 5, 556). D-xylose was obtained in a crystalline form by dissolving the syrup in glacial acetic acid; m.p. and mixed m.p. 142°; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, +93°.5 $\rightarrow$ +19° (c, 0.7% in water). It gave an osazone, m.p. 158° and dimethylacetal of dibenzylidene-D-xylose, m.p. 210° (cf. Breddy and Jones, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 739).

The Barium Salt (B).—The precipitate of the barium salt (B) was freed from non-acidic reducing sugars by refluxing several times with alcohol. It had Ba, 26.2; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, +15° (c, 1.5% in water). The barium salt of D-glucuronic acid, *i. e.* $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_7\text{Ba}$, requires Ba, 26.1%; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, +15° (c, 1.1% in water) (Hirst and Jones, *ibid.*, 1938, 1179). The barium salt was converted into uronic acid and was oxidised by nitric acid. On concentration and keeping, crystals of mucic acid were not obtained. On the other hand, the oxidised product afforded the characteristic crystals of potassium acid saccharate, when treated with 50% KOH and glacial acetic acid in the usual manner.

The quantitative estimation of different sugars in the mucilage furnished pentosan (79.4%) and uronic anhydride (19.5%). These results indicate that the mucilage is composed of D-xylose and D-glucuronic acid in the proportion of 5 : 1 molecules.

Periodate Oxidation of the Mucilage.—The mucilage (0.312 g.), dissolved in water (20 c.c.), was neutralised with *N*/20-NaOH solution (6.66 c.c.), and sodium metaperiodate (20 c.c., 0.3 *M*) was added to it. The mixture was made up to 50 c.c. and kept at 0° in the dark. A portion of the solution (5 c.c.) was withdrawn at different intervals and the amount of formic acid formed, and that of the sodium metaperiodate consumed were determined by usual methods (Whistler and Hickson,

J. Amer. Chem. Soc., 1954, 76, 1672). The results obtained for one equivalent of the mucilage are recorded below.

TABLE I

Time (in hrs.)	0	4	8	12	16	24
Formic acid formed (<i>M</i>)	...	1.9	2.02	2.08	2.09	2.1
NaIO ₄ consumed (<i>M</i>)	...	4.6	4.96	5.05	5.09	5.11

MAHARAJA PRATAPSIKH CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
SIR PARASHURAMBHAU COLLEGE,
POONA-2.

Received July 3, 1956.